

RADx-UP Summative Evaluation Executive Report

Evaluation Timeframe: September 2020 – May 2025

Report Date: June 2025

RADx-UP Tracking and Evaluation Team

RADx-UP Summative Evaluation

Executive Report

RADx-UP Program Evaluation Overview

The National Institutes of Health (NIH) launched the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) program to improve access to rapid, accurate COVID-19 diagnostics to all Americans with a focus on underserved populations disproportionately affected by the coronavirus pandemic across the United States (US), US territories, and Tribal Nations.

The RADx-UP program was comprised of a Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) which provided technical support to all the projects within the RADx-UP consortium: 142 RADx-UP large award research projects (herein referred to as RADx-UP research projects), 25 Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) projects (herein referred to as RP2 projects), and 70 Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) projects (herein referred to as C2G projects).

The CDCC served as the technical support system and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The CDCC was led by teams at two institutions, Duke University and the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill, and co-led by Community-Campus Partnerships for Health (CCPH), a nonprofit membership organization. The four specific aims of the RADx-UP program, specifically for the CDCC, were to:

- 1) Create a community-centered, flexible program infrastructure
- 2) Support a participatory and inclusive community engagement program
- 3) Support research projects with COVID-19 testing guidance and emerging science
- 4) Collect, harmonize, integrate, and disseminate data to scientific and local communities.

The CDCC partnered with a third-party Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team within UNC-Chapel Hill, Abacus Evaluation, to oversee the RADx-UP evaluation. The comprehensive evaluation plan developed for the RADx-UP program assessed how the CDCC program activities improved the RADx-UP program's effectiveness, performance, and community engagement, helping to

understand how the CDCC met its aims. Additionally, the evaluation plan was designed to comprehensively assess the RADx-UP program’s projects’ (RADx-UP research, RP2 and C2G) implementation processes, outcomes, and impact.

The primary purpose of this report is to describe and summarize key evaluation findings across the RADx-UP program from launch in September 2020 through closeout in May 2025.

Evaluation Methods, Analysis and Components

Supported by guiding frameworks which include the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)¹, the Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, and Maintenance Framework (RE-AIM)^{2,3} and the Social Ecological Model (SEM)⁴, the RADx-UP T&E team used a mixed-methods approach to track and evaluate the RADx-UP program’s processes, outcomes, and impacts through the following evaluation components as described in the table below:

Component	Purpose	Analytical Procedures
RADx-UP Research Project Evaluation		
Publication Tracking	Assess research productivity. Data generated are disseminated on the RADx-UP public website and used for other component analyses.	Monthly tracking of all RADx-UP-funded research products through surveys and automated database searches of PubMed and Scopus which tracked 1,214 products through May 2025.
Bibliometric Analysis	Quantitatively assess the scientific impacts of RADx-UP publication and citation data.	Used data from 334 RADx-UP publications tracked through June 30, 2024, to measure interactions with publications and citation impacts.
Network Analysis	Identify patterns of scientific collaborations among authors to assess scientific outputs and impacts.	Conducted a network analysis of co-authorship and publication topic/attribute networks from 334 RADx-UP publications tracked through June 30, 2024.
Content Analysis	Identify the key themes emerging from RADx-UP publications.	Identified study topics/attributes, translational science benefits of testing and vaccination, and thematic categories of impacts across 334 RADx-UP projects’ publications tracked through June 30, 2024.
Project Implementation Survey	Assess the successes, challenges, reach, collaboration, impacts, and sustainability of project implementation activities	Administered a mixed-methods survey to 83 (n=83/138; 61% response rate) research projects’ academic representatives from 2022 to 2023.
Project Interviews		Conducted interviews with 24 community and academic partners associated with 13 research projects in 2023.
Pandemic Caseload Analysis	Show RADx-UP testing reach impacts among socially vulnerable populations by	Utilized RADx-UP research projects’ COVID-19 tests data (Delta, n= 31 projects; Omicron, n= 37 projects) and publicly available caseload and vaccinations rates

	predicting testing rates during the COVID-19 Delta and Omicron variant caseload surges.	data to identify 1) trend/case patterns between COVID-19 testing and positivity counts and 2) significant predictors of COVID-19 cases during variant surges.
Statistical-Spatial Analysis	Assess the benefits of collaborating with community-based organizations for increasing the reach of RADx-UP program testing in underserved areas	Utilized RADx-UP Common Data Elements (CDEs) (26 projects; 115,645 tests across 3,223 codes) and Project Implementation Survey data to assess the benefits of collaborating with community-based organizations for RADx-UP testing reach between communities of high and low social vulnerability index scores.
Agent-Based Modeling	Understand potential impacts of RADx-UP testing reach within communities served	Utilized RADx-UP CDEs across 26 research projects to depict differences in duration of transmission chains among communities with and without RADx-UP testing.

Pilot Projects Evaluation

C2G Evaluation	Evaluate projects' activities, outcomes, impacts, and use of CDCC support and resources	Repeated cross-sectional design and a mixed methods approach to collect data from bi-annual surveys and 6-months after program close-out interviews from 70 C2G projects.
RP2 Evaluation		Repeated cross-sectional design and a mixed methods approach to collect data from bi-monthly surveys from 25 RP2 projects.

CDCC Evaluation

CDCC Evaluation	Assess: 1) the efficiency of CDCC processes; 2) the perceived value of their deliverables; and 3) the satisfaction with CDCC service provision supporting RADx-UP projects.	Mixed-methods survey sent annually to 29 RADx-UP projects academic representatives in 2023.
-----------------	---	---

Key Findings

Who did the RADx-UP program reach?

- Across the RADx-UP program projects, the **five** most frequently reached populations were **Hispanic/Latino, Black/African American, American Indian/Alaskan Native, Hawaii Pacific Islander, and Asian.**

What community outreach strategies for recruitment and retention did the RADx-UP program use? What were the challenges?

- RADx-UP projects effectively recruited participants and promoted COVID-19 awareness using face-to-face recruitment, social media, text messages, and project websites.
- Although projects were ultimately successful in addressing COVID-19 testing and other community needs, some also experienced challenges related to recruitment and retention such as the pool of unvaccinated people to recruit from and participants' struggle to monitor symptoms.

What were the reach and impacts of RADx-UP COVID-19 testing activities?

RADx-UP Projects' Testing Reach and Impacts

- Between June 2020 and December 2024, **495,780** COVID-19 tests were submitted via the NIH RADx-UP Common Data Elements (CDE) (Fig. 1). The most tests with a date were administered in 2022 but tests continued to be administered through 2024.

Figure 1. RADx-UP COVID-19 Tests Submitted, figure developed and designed by the RADx-UP CDCC Communications Team for RADx-UP

- More than half of RADx-UP research projects (n=47/82; 57.5 percent) reported distributing COVID-19 tests which include on-site testing and/or self-testing kits.
- RADx-UP research projects used a variety of strategies to improve testing uptake such as health communication messaging (n=36/83; 43 percent), providing multiple testing locations (n=25/83; 30 percent), employing community health workers (CHW) (n=24/83; 29 percent), and using social media (n=20/83; 24 percent).
- Using culturally responsive and tailored intervention strategies, including leveraging community partnerships to deliver intervention, also increased testing uptake (n=28/83; 34 percent).

Statistical Modeling of RADx-UP COVID-19 Testing Reach and Impacts

- Statistical-spatial analysis findings indicated that RADx-UP research projects collaborating with community-based organizations (CBOs) to increase participant access to project sites, health care, and/or social services, extended their reach to areas characterized by high social vulnerability index (SVI) scores (Map 1 example) when compared to projects that did not actively collaborate with CBOs (Map 2 example).
 - Projects in high SVI areas that engaged CBOs distributed a higher number of COVID-19 tests (9.5 times more tests; 73.8 versus 7.8 tests) when compared to those projects in high SVI areas that did not collaborate with CBOs.
 - 73.8 predicted tests in projects engaging with CBOs in high SVI communities compared to 12.1 predicted tests among projects engaging with CBOs in low SVI communities.

Map 1. Joint distribution of the number of COVID-19 tests and SVI for Project 2 which specified collaboration with CBOs

Map 2. Joint distribution of the number of COVID-19 tests and SVI for Project 74 which did not specify collaboration with CBOs

- Pandemic Caseload Analysis** revealed interesting trends in positive case counts and RADx-UP COVID-19 testing during the Delta and Omicron surge periods. Positive test cases (Fig. 2) and RADx-UP testing (Fig. 3) rates followed a similar pattern with a peak occurring around the end of August 2021 during the Delta surge and in the middle of January 2022 during the Omicron surge. **On occasion when caseloads surged, RADx-UP projects tended to enroll more participants.** Projects within the RADx-UP program were able to increase participant enrollment and testing during the Delta and Omicron surges of positive COVID-19 cases.

Figure 2. Positive cases in the last 7 days during the Delta (left) and Omicron (right) surges

Figure 3. Test enrollment over time during the Delta (left) and Omicron (right) surges

- Agent-based Modeling Analysis** highlighted the impact of RADx-UP testing on reducing infection rates across underserved populations. This finding suggests that expanding testing outreach to medium risk communities could significantly reduce infection rates compared to low and high-risk communities. When modeling and comparing the maximum possible infections with and without RADx-UP testing by plotting the Probability Density Function (PDF) of peak infections obtained, with RADx-UP testing, the mean peak infection was estimated to be around 20 people, whereas without RADx-UP testing, the mean peak infection is estimated to be around 90 people. This analysis provided further evidence that RADx-UP testing played an important role in minimizing infection within targeted communities.

RP2 Testing Reach

- RP2, which funded small, manageable research studies for 12 months, enrolled 6,363 participants and had multiple key benefits (Fig. 4).
- RP2 projects used novel strategies and interventions such as software applications, vending machines, and COVID-flu combination testing to reach underserved populations and settings.
- A total of 6,995 COVID-19 tests were administered throughout the program.

BY THE NUMBERS

RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Projects at a Glance

Collected in the RADx-UP Publications Dashboard as of May, 2023

PUBLISHED MAY 2023

Figure 4. RADx-UP RP2 key benefits at a glance, figure developed and designed by the RADx-UP CDCC Communications Team for RP2

C2G Testing Reach

- C2G provides direct costs to support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives.
- C2G projects testing efforts reached approximately 168,000 people within their communities.
- C2G project activities to increase testing access and uptake included generating resources and materials for COVID-19 testing, engaging trusted community members and organizations to facilitate testing, and providing training and education.

How did the RADx-UP program engage and collaborate with communities?

- **Effective Multi-level Partnerships:** Almost two-thirds ($n=52/80$; 65 percent) of RADx-UP research projects formed community-based partnerships to overcome implementation barriers, address recruitment challenges, and build trust within target communities.
 - More than half ($n=19/29$; 66 percent) of RP2 projects and most ($n=49/55$; 89 percent) C2G projects reported partnerships with community-based organizations/non-profit organizations.
 - **Community-based partners actively contributed** to RADx-UP projects' planning and implementation, engaging in outreach, recruitment, retention, study design, data collection, and utilizing findings to enhance project implementation.
- **Active Community Committees:** Community advisory boards ($n=38/83$; 46 percent) played a crucial role in providing guidance on testing strategies and tailoring interventions.

How satisfied were RADx-UP program projects with CDCC services and what are the opportunities for improvement?

Overall, RADx-UP program projects were satisfied with CDCC administrative support and responsiveness.

- **RADx-UP-** most RADx-UP research projects were satisfied with CDCC's staff professionalism ($n=31/35$; 89 percent), helpfulness ($n=30/35$; 86 percent), ease of accessing service support ($n=30/35$; 86 percent), promptness of services ($n=29/35$; 83 percent) and implementation of project feedback ($n=28/35$; 80 percent).

- Research projects needed **more clarity on expectations** for (and changes in) CDCC workflow goals, processes, and services, especially around close-out activities and other end-of-grant support.
- **RP2-** projects were satisfied with CDCC's administrative support with respect to cultural competency and responsiveness, knowledge in resolving project issues, onboarding and training resources, and response time to requests.
 - To reduce challenges because of the short funding period and rapid funding cycles, projects suggested that the NIH and CDCC could **extend grant funding periods** for future pilot programs.
- **C2G-** Overall, **85 percent (n=49/55)** of C2G projects reported satisfaction with CDCC's administrative support.
 - Suggested areas to improve CDCC support included **simplifying** the application process, **increasing flexibility** in some of the grant requirements, and **supporting collaboration** among projects.

What were some of the RADx-UP programs' benefits for and impacts on communities?

- **Community and Public Health Benefits:** The RADx-UP program provides testing in underserved communities, particularly valuable during times of strained public health resources. Using community engagement strategies (for example, understanding barriers and facilitators of uptake, using community health workers to deliver culturally tailored telehealth education sessions) helped to increase COVID-19 testing uptake and accessibility among different target communities.
- **Economic Benefits:** Over half (**56 percent**) of the RADx-UP research projects provided economic benefits, primarily by minimizing test costs (**n=38/83; 46 percent**), time to complete tests (**n=33/83; 40 percent**), and time to receive test results (**n=28/83; 34 percent**).
- **Pandemic Preparedness:** Survey results suggest that many RADx-UP research projects' activities (**n=59/82; 72 percent**), especially **COVID-19 testing (n=43/47; 91 percent)**, are **agile and replicable**, contributing to **improved pandemic preparedness** in underserved communities.

What were the implementation successes achieved by RADx-UP projects?

RADx-UP Projects Increased COVID-19 Testing Uptake

- **Testing Accessibility and Procurement:** Most RADx-UP research projects ($n=39/47$; 83 percent) indicated success in increasing testing accessibility. Many ($n=10/15$; 67 percent) that experienced challenges were able to easily connect with the CDCC for support to mitigate procurement challenges.
- **Testing Resources and Promotional Strategies:** RADx-UP research projects most frequently utilized a variety of community-based outreach strategies such as utilizing health communication messaging ($n=36/83$; 43 percent), providing testing locations ($n=25/83$; 30 percent), employing community health workers (CHW) ($n=24/83$; 29 percent), and using social media ($n=20/83$; 24 percent) to improve testing and vaccination uptake.

Culturally Tailored Approaches: RADx-UP research projects ($n=28/83$; 34 percent) reported employing culturally responsive strategies as an approach to increase testing uptake, such as hiring staff from the community, providing translation services, and crafting culturally appropriate messaging.

Implementation Successes from RADx-UP Research Project Partnerships

- **Active Community Engagement:** The active involvement of community advisory boards ($n=38/83$; 46 percent) and steering committees ($n=5/83$; 6 percent) played a crucial role in providing guidance on testing strategies, tailoring interventions, and facilitating bi-directional learning between academic and community partners.
- **Building Community Capacity:** Community-based partners actively contributed to research projects' planning, implementation, and dissemination of findings. RADx-UP research projects increased the research capacity of community-based partners by providing research skills training ($n=28/83$; 34 percent) and leadership opportunities ($n=46/83$; 55 percent).
- **Cultural Responsiveness:** RADx-UP research projects demonstrated cultural responsiveness by employing diverse staff ($n=49/83$; 59 percent), providing training in culturally responsive care ($n=37/83$; 44.6 percent), and using plain language in research products ($n=35/83$; 42 percent).

- **Addressing Social Determinants of Health (SDOH) needs:** Beyond COVID-19 interventions, a few research projects' partnership collaborations (n=2) addressed broader social needs, such as cash assistance and food distribution, with many (n=52/80;65 percent) reporting that they connected participants to healthcare and social services.

What were the implementation challenges faced by projects within the RADx-UP program?

- **COVID-19 Testing Supply and Uptake:** Eighteen (18) RADx-UP research projects faced testing supply issues, staffing challenges, changes/restrictions in FDA and NIH testing guidelines (also experienced by RP2 projects), and difficulties in restocking specific testing kit brands. Uptake challenges included low attendance at walk-up clinics, minimal engagement in repeat testing, and testing fatigue.
- **Project Administration:** Twenty-eight (28) RADx-UP research projects and some C2G projects described dealing with staff shortages, turnover, limited capacity, and funding.
- **Challenges with Participant Engagement:** Eighteen (18) RADx-UP research projects reported facing recruitment and retention challenges due to waning COVID-19 interest, logistical issues, and staff constraints. Of the 13 RP2 projects that reported challenges, the most common were related to enrollment and testing reporting.
- **Partnership Coordination and Community Capacity:** Eleven (11) RADx-UP research projects described difficulties in coordinating and engaging diverse stakeholders, securing support, and addressing resource constraints. RADx-UP program projects (RADx-UP research, RP2, and C2G) encountered capacity limitations, particularly in engaging partners and community-based organizations.
- **Data-Related:** Thirty-two (32) research projects described challenges with data collection, analysis, and dissemination due to the rapid evolution of the pandemic, COVID-19 fatigue, staffing shortages, and lack of data science expertise.

What types of scholarly and non-scholarly products did the RADx-UP program projects develop?

- **Number of Products:** As of May 2025, the T&E team tracked **1,214 total RADx-UP program products** which included **888 scholarly products** (387 publications, 409 conference presentations, 90 extramural grants, 2 intramural grants) and **326 non-scholarly products**.
- **Most Disseminated Products:** Most RADx-UP products were **conference presentations** ($n=409$), followed by **scholarly publications** ($n=387$) and **non-scholarly products** (e.g., websites, blog posts, radio shows, videos, news articles, etc.) ($n=326$).
- **Comparison across 2021-2025:** RADx-UP program scholarly publications were produced consistently across the project lifecycle (Fig. 5). The **annual peak publication count** took place in 2022 with a **195 percent (+82 products)** increase and in 2023 with a **157 percent (+66 products)** increase when compared to 2021 ($n=42$ publications). The annual publication count still remained higher in 2024 ($n=92$ publications) than 2021. Although **20** articles were published in 2025, the count as tracked through May 2025 could increase if projects and the program continue to publish final manuscripts.

Figure 5. RADx-UP scholarly publication count by year, 2020-2024*

*RADx-UP publications were tracked through May 2025; since the 2025 count was not for the entire year, it is not shown

What did RADx-UP program scholarly collaboration for research dissemination look like?

- The network analysis of 334 RADx-UP publications which assessed scientific collaboration showed 1163 authors grouped into 29 clusters (co-authorship components).
- To assess scholarly collaboration for research dissemination, the network analysis measured *median degree centrality*, a measure of direct connections, i.e., the median number of co-authors an author was connected to, and *percentage of within project ties*, i.e., the percentage of an authors' connections that were within their RADx-UP project. From 2022-2024, *scholarly collaboration on RADx-UP publications increased each year*. In 2022, the median degree was 11 and 84% of all ties within the RADx-UP publication network were just within projects. In 2024, the median degree increased to 15 and within project ties decreased to 33%, showing authors increased connections with other co-authors and more of those connections were outside of their own projects.
- To understand community involvement in scholarly collaboration, the network analysis measured representation of co-authors on publications from organizations outside of academia. Co-authors affiliated with organizations outside of academia were present in most clusters. Community co-author representation increased in the network from 2022-2024. Community Organizations were present in 18% of clusters in 2022, 37% in 2023, and 41% in 2024.

	2022	2023	2024
<i>Median degree</i>	11	12	15
<i>%Within project ties</i>	84%	63%	33%
<i>%Community partners</i>	18%	37%	41%

- The network analysis also included a correlational network of publication topics/attributes, i.e., characteristics of the publication content (for example, study population, study setting, study design, community outreach strategies, translational science benefits of testing and vaccination research) (Fig. 6). *Community outreach* emerged as the *most central publication topic/ attribute* and contributed most to holding the publications network together such that it connected topics that might not otherwise be connected. This highlights *the importance of the space that RADx-UP provided for community-engaged research to thrive*.

Publication Attribute Correlation Network

Figure 6. RADx-UP publication (n=334) topic/attribute correlational network, showing strength of correlations among topic/attributes of publications. Community outreach strategies emerged as the most central publication topic/attribute in this network analysis.

How did RADx-UP publications advance knowledge on COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-engaged research?

Content Analysis

- **Most common key learning categories** from 334 publications were: 1) *social, ethical, and behavioral factors (SEBI) influencing testing (n=73)*, 2) *SEBI factors influencing vaccination (n=77)*, and 3) *impacts of collaborative partnerships and community engagement (n=79)*.
- **SEBI factors influencing testing and vaccination uptake:** Publications reviewed noted disparities in testing and vaccination hesitancy, motivation, access, and uptake exist among diverse underserved populations. Initiatives like in-reach and outreach through clinics, mobile units, reduced-cost/free testing and vaccination, employer-sponsored resources, and at-home testing improved access and uptake to COVID-19 testing and vaccination.
- **Structural Barriers to Testing and Vaccination:** Seventeen (17) publications cited different structural barriers to testing. These barriers include transportation or driving times, location of centers or services, inflexible work schedules, fear of losing employment while getting tested, wait times or scheduling, fear of exposure while waiting to be tested, beliefs about testing, and the cost of testing. Twenty-two (22) publications cited one or more structural barriers to COVID-19 vaccination that were parallel to testing barriers.

- **Impact of Community Engagement and Collaborative Partnerships:** Seventy-nine (79) publications coded under **impacts of collaborative partnerships and community engagement** described these impacts in detail within the following areas:

- Utilized multi-sector partnerships to implement, adapt, and promote testing or vaccination
- Strengthened recruitment and data collection
- Improved community capacity for research and community workforce development
- Informed health messaging, outreach, and dissemination strategies
- Used community advisory board and community-based participatory research methods to guide research implementation
- Built sustainable trusted relationships within communities
- Evaluated the impacts and strengths of community engagement.

What were some of the bibliometric impacts from RADx-UP publications?

- RADx-UP publications (n=334) focused on underserved and vulnerable communities and populations with the **five** most frequent being **Hispanic/Latino (n=84 publications)**, **children/adolescents (n=64 publications)**, **Black/African American (n=63 publications)**, **low socioeconomic status (n=44 publications)**, and **rural (n=36 publications)**.
- The bibliometric analysis found a **strong research influence** of RADx-UP publications.
 - From the Scopus database, **328** articles had **2,641** citations.
 - Research influence as measured by time- and field- normalized relative citation ratio (RCR) scores for RADx-UP publications (178 RADx-UP publications were assigned RCR values at the time of the analysis) showed that **RADx-UP publications had a greater-than-typical citation rate (average (mean) RCR score=2.07)** compared to NIH-funded papers in the same field and year.
 - The journals with the largest quantity of RADx-UP scholarly publications were the **American Journal of Public Health (n=41 publications)** and **Pediatrics (n=33 publications)** which both published special supplements with a RADx-UP focus.

Journal	Supplement Date	Focus
<i>American Journal of Public Health</i>	Nov 2022 & May 2024	Community testing in underserved populations; community-engaged research
<i>Pediatrics</i>	July 2023	COVID-19 testing and protocols for safe school reopening

- Altmetric data, which captures insights into the ways people interact with research products such as mentions and citations in news, social media, and policy, showed that RADx-UP program findings from 390 publications translated beyond scholarly audiences, for example, there were 736 news counts and 69 policy citations.
- Two coders utilized a policy framework to understand how RADx-UP publications had informed five policy levers: access; resource allocation; data; communication; payment and three foundational components: community engagement; cross-sector partnerships; regulatory guidance.⁵ The most frequently coded policy lever was data while the most frequently coded foundational component was cross-sector partnerships.

To what extent will RADx-UP program impacts be sustained?

RADx-UP Research Projects

- More than half of RADx-UP research projects (n=57/82; 70 percent) indicated that their community engagement strategies will continue and almost a third (n=27/82; 33 percent) have secured or will seek additional funding to sustain other project activities and interventions.
- Additionally, some research projects (n=39/57; 68 percent) indicated that priority populations will continue to have access to project-related healthcare and social services.

RP2

- RP2 projects plan to use their project data as evidence to justify feasibility when applying for additional funding.

C2G

- Organizations affiliated with C2G projects reported that they continued COVID-19 testing and education activities including partnerships within their communities.

CDCC

- Through its *Sankofa Project* initiative, the CDCC committed to leaving a rich legacy of data, published articles, resources and toolkits including best practices for pandemic preparedness and community-engaged research.
- The *Sankofa Project* Taskforce: 1) engaged the consortium - developing and refining learning categories; defining audiences; and identifying legacy products; and 2) created and curated an asset catalog – an inventory of RADx-UP program products with 314 of them publicly available.
- The taskforce also developed a RADx-UP Playbook with contextualization of legacy products and lessons learned across the consortium for future use by multiple audiences.

Conclusions

- Across multiple analyses, key summative evaluation findings show that the RADx-UP program improved COVID-19 testing access and uptake across the US, US territories, and Tribal Nations while strengthening academic and community partnerships for public health programming and research.
- Many of the program activities that benefit underserved communities, including testing, healthcare and social need services, will continue in some capacity after project closeout.
- The RADx-UP program advanced scientific knowledge about COVID-19 testing and community engaged research while creating a space for collaborative research to thrive. The consortium approach to supporting many projects was largely successful, albeit with suggestions for improvement, with most program projects indicating satisfaction or high satisfaction overall with CDCC support and resources. This overall project satisfaction with CDCC support and resources points to a successful model for technical assistance to multiple awardees which could be modeled in future research consortia.

- RADx-UP consistently produced scholarly and non-scholarly products on COVID-19 testing and community-engaged research from start-up to closeout, including publications in peer-reviewed journals, which have been disseminated to multiple audiences and on multiple platforms thereby impacting researchers, supporting policy decision-making, and providing emerging evidence in accessible ways to communities.

Additionally, the knowledge gained from the initiative will be packaged for accessibility and made available to inform future community and public health initiatives further extending the RADx-UP program impact.

- Summative evaluation findings indicate that the RADx-UP program successfully achieved its aims to create a flexible infrastructure responsive to projects' needs, support a participatory and inclusive community engagement program, disseminate findings to multiple audiences, and contribute to scientific knowledge on COVID-19 testing and community-engaged research.

-
1. Luke DA, Sarli CC, Suiter AM, et al. The Translational Science Benefits Model: A New Framework for Assessing the Health and Societal Benefits of Clinical and Translational Sciences. *Clin Transl Sci*. 2018;11:77-84. doi:10.1111/cts.12495
 2. Glasgow RE, Vogt TM, Boles SM. Evaluating the public health impact of health promotion interventions: the RE-AIM framework. *American journal of public health*. 1999 Sep;89(9):1322-7.
 3. Kwan BM, McGinnes HL, Ory MG, Estabrooks PA, Waxmonsky JA, Glasgow RE. RE-AIM in the real world: use of the RE-AIM framework for program planning and evaluation in clinical and community settings. *Frontiers in public health*. 2019 Nov 22;7:345.
 4. McLeroy KR, Bibeau D, Steckler A, Glanz K. An Ecological Perspective on Health Promotion Programs. *Health Education Quarterly*. 1988;15(4):351-377. doi:10.1177/109019818801500401
 5. Thoumi A, Kaalund K, Bond S, et al. Scaling Up Equitable Access to Community-Based COVID-19 Testing: Strategies from the RADx-UP Initiative. Durham, NC: Duke Clinical Research Institute; Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy; UNC Center for Health Equity Research; May 10, 2022. <https://healthpolicy.duke.edu/sites/default/files/2022-05/Scaling%20Up%20Equitable%20Access%20RADX.pdf>